

SYNERGISTIC ROLE OF PANCHAKARMA AND VIDDDHA KARMA IN ADHD: AN AYURVEDIC CASE-BASED INSIGHT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Attention-deficit Hyperactivity disorder is the most common neurobehavioral disorder in childhood, affecting social, academic, and occupational functioning. It is marked by inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity. In Ayurveda, such psychiatric and behavioral disturbances are discussed under *Unmada Vyadhi*. These conditions are associated with the vitiation of Dhee, Dhriti, and Smriti, leading to *Prajnaparadha*—the impairment of mental faculties and judgment. **Aims and Objectives-** Key findings reveal the efficacy of *Ayurvedic* formulations and therapies in ADHD, addressing underlying imbalances in the body's *Doshas*. **Material and Method -** A 5-year-6-month-old male child was selected for the study, presenting with clinical symptoms of hyperactivity in daily activities. He does not follow commands given by parents or teachers, shows poor eye contact with strangers, and has had unclear speech for 7-8 months. **Therapeutic intervention-** The patient was administered Ayurvedic oral medications along with *Bal Panchakarma* and *Viddha Karma* procedures. **Result-** Notable reduction in hyperactivity, better response to commands, and improved social interaction. **Conclusion-** *Medhya drugs* with *Nadi Swedana* and *Viddha Karma (Shamana and Shodhana Chikitsa)* together showed effective results in managing ADHD symptoms by balancing *Vata & Pitta* and enhancing neurological function.

KEYWORDS: *Shamana Chikitsa, Nadi Swedana, Viddha Karma, Shodhan Karma.*

INTRODUCTION

ADHD (Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder) is one of the most common neurobehavioral disorders in children and a prevalent chronic condition among school-aged individuals. It is characterized by inattention, distractibility, poor impulse control, motor restlessness, and difficulty sustaining attention.^[1] ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder, primarily involving imbalances in dopamine and norepinephrine neurotransmitters, which regulate various cognitive functions. Globally, the prevalence of ADHD is estimated to be around 5–10% in school-aged children. In Uttarakhand, prevalence based on teacher reports was found to be 11.8%, and 1.75% when assessed using both parent and teacher evaluations.^[2]

While Ayurveda does not mention ADHD directly, symptoms resembling the condition are discussed under

Unmada Vyadhi. It can be manifested as a *Vata-Pitta* predominant condition. In this, *Manovaha Srotodushti* occurs with predominance of *Rajas* and *Tamas Manshik guna*. The core disturbance lies in the vitiation of *Dhee* (rational thinking), *Dhriti* (intellect/stability), and *Smriti* (memory), leading to impaired sensory perception, hyperactivity, impulsivity, and inattentiveness. Modern medicine offers treatments such as psychostimulants, which may reduce symptoms but are not curative and often have side effects. In contrast, Ayurveda recommends *Medhya Rasayanas* as part of *Shamana Chikitsa* and *Murdha Taila* under *Shodhana Chikitsa*, offering a holistic and safer approach to managing such disorders.

CASE REPORT

Patient information- A 5-year- 6-month-old male patient visited the Kaumarbhritya Outpatient Department

on 2nd March 2025 with the chief complaints of hyperactivity in his daily activities, poor eye contact with strangers, and not following commands given by teachers and parents. The patient also has difficulty speaking clearly, around 7 to 8 months. The patient took speech therapy for 30 days around 1 month ago, which led to mild improvement in speech.

With this complaint, the patient came to the hospital for further management.

Past History: No significant.

Birth History: The child was delivered at full term via normal vaginal delivery at a hospital. Birth weight was 1.8 kg (low birth weight). The child cried immediately after birth but was admitted to the NICU for two days due to low birth weight.

Developmental History: Has a history of delayed developmental milestones as per developmental age.

Family History: Not significant.

Clinical findings

Physical Examination- The patient was examined according to *Ayurvedic Pariksha*, and findings were summarized in Table 1.

Ashtavidhpariksha (eight-fold examination)
<i>Nadi:</i> Vata Pradhan Pitta Anubandhi
<i>Mutra:</i> Peetabh Varn, Aavrutti- 4-5 times
<i>Mala:</i> Shushka, Niram, Aavrutti – 2 times
<i>Jivha:</i> Lipta (slightly whitish)
<i>Shabda:</i> Aspastha
<i>Sparsha:</i> Ruksha, Samsheetoshana
<i>Drikka:</i> Shweta varn
<i>Aakriti:</i> Samanya

Immunization History: Immunized till date

Baseline findings- The patient's general condition was average, has good appetite, and has a habit of eating packed food 4 times/week along with **screen time of about 4-5 hr /day**. Period of sleep is regular. Anthropometry measures are - weight of 17.10 kg, a height of 107 cm, a body mass index of 14.9 kg/m², and mid-upper arm circumferences of both arms at 13.5 cm. The patient's vitals were 98.7°F of temperature, 80 beats/min of pulse rate, 24 breaths/min of respiratory rate, and 100/70 mmHg of blood pressure.

Mental Status: Restlessness, Difficulty maintaining eye contact, and having frequent distraction during conversation.

On systemic examination, the patient was conscious and well oriented; on auscultation of the heart, S1, S2 were heard, the chest was clear with air entry to lungs bilaterally equal, and gastrointestinal system examination showed that the abdomen was soft, non-tender with normal bowel sound.

Dosha	<i>Sharirika -Prana, Udana & Vyana Vayu, Sadhaka, Alochaka Pitta</i> Manshika -Raja, Tama
Dushya	<i>Mana</i>
Agni	<i>Vishmagni</i>
Shrotas	<i>Manovah</i>
Shrotodushti	<i>Attipravrti</i>
Adhithana	<i>Hridaya</i>

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

Treatment Protocol: After a thorough evaluation of the patient's clinical condition, including detailed history taking from the mother regarding the child's diet, habits, and present illness, a treatment plan was formulated. The

child was advised internal medications along with *Bal Panchakarma* and *Viddha Karma*.

Intervention: The patient was treated with two sittings of therapy along with oral medications for 15 days, followed by 15 days of oral medication alone.

Treatment duration & Period of assessment - 60 days, The patient was assessed at interval of 15 days

OPD visit	Medication	Duration	Advice
First (3/03/2025) visit	Syp <i>Shankhpushpi</i> - 1 tsf bid Syp Mentat- 1 tsf bid <i>Kumar Kalyank Ras</i> – 30mg <i>Parval Panchamrit Ras</i> - 30mg <i>Amrita Satva</i> - 30 mg <i>Ashwgandha Churna</i> - 500mg ----- 1*3 with honey <i>Shiroabhyang</i> with <i>Jyotishmati</i> Oil in the morning <i>Vacha Moola</i> with honey- Local application	15 days	Increase water intake (5-6 g/day). Avoid junk /packed food. Stop Screen time completely.

	<p>Bal Panchkarma Therapy- 1)Sarvang Abhyang with Bala Oil 2)Sarvang Nadi Sweda 3)Shirotalam with Jyotishmati Oil 4)Viddhkarma at Shankh Pardesh</p>		
Second visit (18/03/2025)	<p>Syp Shankhpushi- 1 tsf bid Syp Mentat- 1 tsf bid Kumar Kalyank Ras – 30mg Parval Panchamrit Ras- 30mg Amrita Satva- 30 mg Ashwgandha Churna- 500mg</p> <hr/> <p>1*3 with honey Shiroabhyang with Jyotishmati Oil in the morning Vacha Moola with honey- Local application</p> <p>6)Viddhkarma at Shankh Pardesh</p>	15 days	
Third visit (3/04/2025)	<p>Syp Shankhpushi- 1 tsf bid Syp Mentat- 1 tsf bid Kumar Kalyank Ras – 30mg Parval Panchamrit Ras- 30mg Amrita Satva- 30 mg Ashwgandha Churna- 500mg</p> <hr/> <p>1*3 with honey Shiroabhyang with Jyotishmati Oil Vacha Moola with honey- Local application</p> <p>Bal Panchkarma Therapy 1)Sarvang Abhyang with Bala Oil 2)Sarvang Nadi Sweda 3)Shirotalam with Jyotishmati Oil 4)Viddhkarma at Shankh Pardesh</p>	15 days	
Four visit (18/04/2025)	<p>Syp Shankhpushi- 1 tsf bid Syp Mentat- 1 tsf bid Kumar Kalyank Ras – 30mg Parval Panchamrit Ras- 30mg Amrita Satva- 30 mg Ashwgandha Churna- 500mg</p> <hr/> <p>1*3 with honey 4. Shiroabhyang with Jyotishmati Oil Vacha Moola with honey- Local application</p>	15 days	

Fig 1. Nadi Swedna

Fig 2. Shriotalam

Fig 3. Viddhkaram at Shankha Pardesh

Lifestyle modification & parents counselling:

Pranayama for 5 minutes daily, Fixed bedtime, Stop screen time completely. Parents are guided on how to create a structured, supportive, and predictable environment at home.

Outcome Measures: Vanderbilt ADHD Diagnostic Parent Rating Scale (VADPRS) and Clinical observation.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Regression of the patient's symptoms was observed over the course of 2 months. The child exhibited significant improvement:

- Increased attention span and ability to concentrate on tasks.
- Reduced impulsivity and aggression.
- Enhanced ability to follow structured routines.
- Improved mood stability.

Teachers and parents reported noticeable behavioral changes, with greater engagement in school activities and better peer interactions. During the treatment, no minor or major complications were observed in the patient.

DISCUSSION

Ayurveda sees ADHD as an imbalance of Vata and Pitta doshas, leading to hyperactivity, impulsiveness, and inattention. Treatment aims to restore balance through herbs, detoxification, diet, and lifestyle changes, addressing root causes rather than just symptoms.

Role of herbal Remedies in ADHD Management

Shankhpushpi is considered as *Medhya Rasayana* in Ayurvedic texts. It possesses *Katu* and *Kashaya rasa*, *Guru*, *Snigdha*, *Sara*, and *Pichchhila gunas*, *Ushna veerya*, and *Madhura vipaka*. It is known for actions like *Medhakrit* (indicates its role in promoting cognitive functions), *Swarakara* (signifies its benefit in enhancing vocal clarity and strength), and *Grahabhuta-didoshhara* (alleviating afflictions caused by negative energies or entities). **Syp Mentet** is a poly herbal formulation containing *-Bhrami*, *Vishnukranta*, *Tagara*, *Vacha*, *Amla*,

Mandukparani, etc, exhibits the cumulative effects such as neuro-protective, anxiolytic, antidepressant, and antioxidant properties leading to a calming effect on the brain. **Kumar Kalyan Ras-** is a potent rejuvenator with *Tridosha* balancing action, especially pacifying Kapha and Vata. It targets vital tissues like lymphatic fluids, digestive enzymes, blood tissues, bone marrow, and the body's immunity, and acts primarily on the gastrointestinal system. **Ashwagandha** has adaptogenic properties that help regulate cortisol levels, leading to reduced stress and anxiety, common in ADHD. It also improves focus, attention, and impulse control through its antioxidant and GABA-modulating properties. **Giloy Satva** is particularly effective in Pitta disorders, aiding in digestion, AMA (toxin) clearance, liver function, and providing antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory benefits. **Vacha**, with its *Tikta rasa*, has a powerful effect on the nervous system. It is well known for its Vata-balancing and *Medhya* properties. When taken with honey, Vacha is traditionally used to support speech development by strengthening the vocal cords and improving speech clarity. The cumulative effect of these drugs acts as neuro-protective, anxiolytic, Anti-inflammatory, antidepressant, and Immunomodulator.

Shiroabhyanga is a rejuvenating Ayurvedic head massage using dosha-specific, herb-infused oils that offer both therapeutic and calming benefits. It improves blood and oxygen flow to the brain, supports lymphatic drainage, and is highly effective in relieving fatigue and managing insomnia, promoting deep, restful sleep. *Jyotishmati*, a renowned *Medhya Rasayana*, in its oil form, penetrates deep tissues due to its *Sukshma*, *Tikshna*, and *Vyavayi* properties. Its *Ushna guna*, *Katu rasa*, and *Ushna veerya* stimulate *Pitta* and *Sadhakagni*, enhancing *Medha* and clearing *Kapha-Tama Avarana*, thus improving memory, intellect, and benefiting psychiatric conditions.

Role of Panchkarma and Viddhkarma Therapies

Sarvanga Abhyanga is a synchronized full-body massage using herbal oils applied in the direction of

arterial flow. It stimulates lymphatic drainage, improves circulation, reduces blood pressure, and aids detoxification. It pacifies Vata and Kapha, relieves fatigue, promotes sleep, and strengthens the body. Bala Taila enhances its *Brimhana*, *Santarpana*, *Medhya*, and *Rasayana* effects, supporting mental clarity and reducing stress, and promoting overall emotional and cognitive well-being.

Sarvanga Nadi Sweda is a sudation therapy where medicated steam is directed to the whole body through a tube. It boosts blood flow, enhances nerve conduction, and improves collagen flexibility, relieving stiffness. Acting as *Sthambhaghna*, *Gauravaghna*, and *Sheetaghna*, it helps balance Vata and Kapha.

Shirotalam involves applying medicated pastes or oils to the scalp for neurological and psychological balance. It pacifies *Prana Vata*, *Sadhaka Pitta*, and *Tarpaka Kapha*, promoting calmness, better circulation, and improved stress response, easing symptoms like anxiety and mental fatigue.

Viddhkarama- It involves therapeutic puncturing of specific points using a fine needle. It helps regulate Vata and Kapha by inducing lightness and promoting *Vatanulomana*. The procedure leads to subtle *Rakta Srava*, clearing blocked *Srotas*, improving circulation, and aiding detoxification. According to *Acharya Shusruta* *Viddh* should be performed at *Shankh Pradesh* in *Unmada & Apasmar Vyadi*. The *Shankha Pradesh* is closely associated with vital head channels, and *Viddha Karma* here helps pacify doshas accumulated in the brain region.

CONCLUSION

According to Ayurveda, ADHD is primarily caused by the vitiation of *Vata* dosha and *Pitta* dosha, particularly *Prana*, *Udana*, *Vyana Vata*, and *Sadhak Pitta*, *AlochakaPitta* which disrupts *Manoarthas* and *Manokarmas*, leading to symptoms like inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity. Unlike conventional treatments, Ayurveda emphasizes holistic healing through herbal remedies, Panchakarma therapies, diet, and lifestyle changes. The key to management lies in balancing aggravated *Vata & Pitta* and restoring the proper functioning of *Agni*. Herbs used in ADHD treatment should possess *Ama Pachana*, *Agni Deepana* properties, while also pacifying *Vata and Pitta* doshas. Additionally, *Medhya*, *Rasayana* enhance cognition, reduce stress, and support mental clarity. Therapies such as *Shiroabhyanga*, *Nadi Sweda*, and *Viddha Karma* calm the nervous system, improve circulation, and promote detoxification. This integrative approach nourishes the mind, pacifies doshas, and enhances *Sadhakagni* and *Medha*, offering a natural, effective, and sustainable way to manage ADHD.

Declaration of patient consent- The authors confirm patient and parental consent was obtained for

publication, with efforts to ensure confidentiality, though complete anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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